

Some days in my life I hate everyone but not Sudha. Because she is my other half. The sister of my heart I can tell Sudha everything I feel and not have to explain any of it. She'll look at me with those big unblinking eyes and smile a tiny smile and I'll know she understands me perfectly.

Like no-one else in the entire world does.

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In feminist theory Bell Hooks remarks on female bonding:

We must learn to live and work in solidarity. We must learn the true meaning and value of sisterhood.

The genre of novel in literature, was diplomatically used by women writers to explore and share their experiences. The recognition of the bond of woman-woman relationship was accepted socially due to the rigid male-female compartmentalization.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni focuses on the sisterhood relationship in her novel 'Sister Of My Heart' she studies how Sudha and Anju, sisters protect each other from feeling lonely, unloved, guilty, self-conscious and fearful and did not matter whether the sister was younger or older and though the siblings in a family seem to fight endlessly with each other, once they get to adolescence. Two more sisters Nazneen and Hasina appeared in Monica Ali's literary debut *Brick Lane* greeted unanimously unreservedly with a buoyant reception in the western literary arena before it was even published. These two ladies represent Bangladeshi Muslim society.

Monica Ali would not have to wait for ages to get through her novel to the screen; a production company has already snatched it for film and the volleys of tributes it has received, we must put it in context and take these entire hasty accolade with a pinch of salt. Even Chitra's novel *Sister of my Heart* was made into a television series in Tamil and aired in India, as *Anbulla Snegithiye (Loving Friend)*.

Sudha and Anju, the two protagonists of Chitra, are cousins born on the same day, raised up in the same house and finally married on the same day. Their marriage drives a wedge between them geographically separating them, as Sudha moves to Midnapur to stay with her in-laws and Anju moves to U.S. with IT engineer husband. Their lives

changed as their hopes and happiness began to be lied to the men in their lives. But their trust in each other, their bonding stays. Their bonding as a succor against the troubles in a woman's life pregnancy, threat of divorce, miscarriage etc. is significant from feminist point of view forming 'SISTERHOOD' all over the world to present a united front against patriarchal oppression.

Have a glimpse of their childhood in the words of Anju:

"All through childhood we bathed together and ate together, often from the same plate, feeding each other our favorite items: the crunchy brown triangles of parothas, fried egg plant, spongy-sweet rasogollah balls. Our favourite game was acting out the fairy tales. Papi told us, where Sudha was always the princess and I the prince who rescued her. And when we had nightmares, instead of going to our mothers for comfort, we squeezed into one bed and held each other." (2)

Brick Lane is a narration about Nazneen and about her journey to Britain and to her supposed freedom. Nazneen is married off by her father to Chanu, a Bangladeshi immigrant in London who is 'an unspoiled girl from the village.' (3) in the words of her husband, but her own sister Hasina 'kicked against fate (patriarchal system), and rebellious in nature, listened to no one, escapes an arranged marriage, elopes with Malek (her boyfriend) and finally ends up as 'a factory worker, a prostitute and a maid.'

Sisterhood of Nazneen and Hasina is important as it helps them tide over their troubles but the difficulties and adumbrates serve as a reminder that female bonding is a fraught project.

Circumstances didn't crush their relation, distance couldn't freeze their warmth and web length, they all remain green through letters, from Hasina to Nazneen and from Nazneen to Hasina. Look at the bond when Nazneen, who is living in London after marriage writes letter to Hasina...

"Can you believe? We live in block of flat is three storey high. Our place have two room. No veranda but I go up on roof. There is brown stone floor it cool your feet. We have bed with metal spring, a cabinet and two chairs in bedroom. I fold saris and put in box under bed. In living room we has three cane chair, a rug one stool, a crate is only temporary before we getting table. Also paraffin stove I keep under shawl for making tidy. My pot and pans is

keep inside the crate .Hardly any cockroach only one may be two I see time to time.

Even we have nothing I happy .We have love , love is happiness. Sometime I feel to run and jump like goat. This is how we do on way to school .But not much room for running here and I sixteen year old and married woman."

(5)

In the quote of Pradhanya Deshmukh "In the best friendship with women ,there is a closeness that is unique ,a sympathy that comes from somewhere deep and primal in our bodies and heart and doesn't need explanation ,perhaps because of the life -changing experiences we share: menstruation ,child-birth ,menopause .The same tragedies ,physical and emotional threaten uswe take joy in the same small good things of our life....oh ,we fight too. We are sometime furiously competitive and bitchy and exasperated. But ultimately we can be ourselves with each other."(6)

Divakaruni's Sister Of My Heart is the story of two girls .Anju and Sudha raised as close as sisters in a household of women .Anju and sudha are opposites .Where Sudha is beautiful ,romantic and conventional ,Anju is practical , challenges situation and enjoys reading.Anju confronts her mother saying "I bet if I were a boy you wouldn't be saying no to me all the time like this ." (7)

By the choice of her mother for marriage, Sudha was forced by mother-in-law and husband to abort baby girl she emerged rebellious and flew house ,supported by Pishi (upholder of the house) and Anju who suffers blame of her husband for her miscarriage due to extra trial hours to save money for sudha's ticket to America.Anju was also empathized by sudha bestowing character of Rani Laxmibai as a source of inspiration.

Nazneen and Hasina have the same background, but they end up living far away from each other in different cultures ,yet remaining important parts of each other ,live through letters. Often their lives seem to consist of constant struggle and survival, especially Hasina's and they both carry the notion of fate with them .Their mother always taught them to leave everything to Allah and fate. Are they supposed to trust their lives simply to fate and Allah? ,when Nazneen's physic was presented as commodity by her own husband before his friend in a phone call describing about her "Hips are a bit narrow but wide enough to carry children." (8) Anju's husband ,Sunil addicted to American culture .He used to come late ,addicted to alcohol .It was a great cultural shock and out of her imagination. She had to be very careful in using words in front of Sunil due to his criticism about woman . According to Anju `shit' is a very common term in America but she uses the term very carefully only when Sunil is not around because he thinks it isn't ladylike.

Nazneen lives in the heart of London known as Brick

Lane, wherea community of immigrant Bangladesh ilives .She makes her life staying at home and socializes only with members from the Bangladeshi society. She takes permission from her husband even to take English lessons .Gradually she begins to step out from the role of an obedient housewife .Nazneen has had three children and experienced the devastation of losing one of them. She has been married to a man twice her age and fallen in love with a young man with a Bangladeshi background and committed adultery. In the end she is able to make up her own mind and take fate into her own hands after whole life doing the opposite .

Hasina seems to more free than Nazneen who lives inside a society ,whereas Hasina is an outcast, still in the end Nazneen is free and does not need a man to define her ,whereas Hasina is an outcast ,she has once again escaped with a man perhaps in the hope of finally having a family of her own .From this point of view the British society ,more than the Bangladeshi society one ,better enables an immigrant woman to make a life of her own .similar is the case with sudha in India who suffers ill customs and after moving to America she starts spreading her wings to assemble herself and of her daughter. However, it requires strength from a woman to go against the expectations of her own minority group and in addition ,face the possible hostility and racism of the host society.

The story of Pishi ,the loving widowed aunt of Sudha and Anju is another scathing comment on the patriarchal system prevailing in India .She was only eighteen when she lost her husband .She came back to her parents as a widow and followed " society is tyrannical rules"...Pishi recollects :

" I packed away my good saris ,my wedding jewellery ,ate only one meal a day ,no fish or meet ,fasted and played for that ?Every night I soaked my pillows with guilty tears because I was told that it was my bad luck which has caused my husband's death ." (9) and to the rescue of Sudha from unwanted abortion of girl child , not to put vermilion on her head and bindi on forehead .Pishi renders support and says Sudha is old enough to make her own decision .She can no longer be the sleeping princess trusting a prince to kiss her awake.

Going to Hasina's life ,she gets less vacuum to grow herself and life spoils fast . Remember she kicked fate (patriarchal system) even being in her own culture .She couldn't adopt its own culture which was carried forward by Nazneen even in London .There also she wears sarees and covers her head .She breaks the role of a traditional Bangladeshi housewife and becomes an independent woman who still carries her inheritance and religion with her ,but now on her own terms .

Sudha is more sincere and mature than Anju ,even knowing the bitter fact behind the Anju's father death that is her own father was responsible for this. This bitter truth

made distance for a period of time but relation of understanding and relation which can not be explained in words are always embossed on the map of heart.

Banerjee's and Ali's writing affirm that sisterhood is not merely a relation but it is an experience made up of collectivities and multiple journeys. It's an experience that is determined by who travels, where, how and under circumstances. Journey of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's life journey from India to America and Monica Ali's life journey from Bangladesh to Britain presents eyesights of an expatriates where understanding is followed by attempts to adjust, to adopt and to accept. Only the degree of adaption, understanding, devotion, sacrifice is learned so innately in soul relationship and even differs according to the generation.

Work Cited :

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